

Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Pd(II), UO_2^{2+} and VO^{2+} chelates of (α -benzoylmethyl benzylidene-imino) benzene sulphonic acid and 2-(α -benzoylmethyl benzylideneimino) ethane sulphonic acid

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Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Pd(II), UO_2^{2+} and VO^{2+} form solid chelates with (α -benzoylmethyl-benzylideneimino)benzene sulphonic acid (H_2BB) and 2-(α -benzoylmethyl benzylideneimino)ethane sulphonic acid (H_2BE). The stoichiometry and structure of these chelates have been confirmed by elemental analyses, molecular weight, magnetic moment, conductance, u.v. and i.r. spectra. Fe(II), Mn(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), VO^{2+} -chelates display octahedral geometry, Zn(II) and Cd(II) chelates have tetrahedral structures, whereas Pd(II) chelates show a square-planar stereochemistry.

A perusal of the literature¹⁻³ has revealed that no work has been done on the bivalent metal chelates of the Schiff bases derived from *o*-aminobenzene sulphonic acid or 2-aminoethane sulphonic acid and dibenzoyl methane. The two ligands are structurally similar and are expected to behave as biprotic tridentates.

Experimental

Chemicals and apparatus employed in the investigations are the same as reported earlier⁴. The Schiff bases and their solid chelates with Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Zn(II), Cd(II), Pd(II), UO_2^{2+} and VO^{2+} were prepared by the method reported earlier⁵.

The pyridine adducts were also synthesised by the literature procedure⁶.

The results of elemental analyses, molecular weight, magnetic moment, conductance and electro-nic spectral data of the chelates are summarised in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The uv spectra of the metal chelates and their adducts under discussion (Table 1) suggest an octahedral stereochemistry for the Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II), Pd(II) and VO^{2+} -chelates. The chelates gave satisfactory elemental analyses and display 1:1 (metal-ligand) stoichiometry. Their composition may be expressed by $[\text{ML}.n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or $\text{Py}]$, where M=metal ion. Thermogravimetric analysis suggest a weight loss compared to three

water or pyridine molecules ($n=3$) when $\text{M}=\text{Mn(II)}$, Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II) or Cu(II), two water or pyridine molecules ($n=2$) when $\text{M}=\text{VO}^{2+}$ and one water or pyridine molecule ($n=1$) when $\text{M}=\text{Zn(II)}$, Cd(II), Pd(II) or UO_2^{2+} .

The magnetic moments (Table 1) indicate the presence of 5,4,3,2,1 and 1 unpaired electron respectively in Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), Cu(II) and VO^{2+} -chelates and show their paramagnetic character. The remaining chelates were found diamagnetic. From the magnetic moments it is apparent that there is no metal-metal bonding in the chelates and hence spin-exchange does not take place and they exist as monomer which is also evident from their molecular weights (Table 1).

The negligibly small conductance values (3.5 - 7.3) of the compounds in dioxane and DMF suggest them to be non-electrolytes.

The molecular weights of the metal chelates and their adducts (Table 1) were determined by Gallenkamp semimicro ebulliometer in dioxan. A perusal of these values suggest their monomeric nature.

In the i.r. spectra of H_2BB and H_2BE five bands were observed in the ranges of 3360-3370, 1680-1690, 1635-1650, 1600-1610 and 1080-1100 cm^{-1} which correspond⁷ to νOH , $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$, $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$, $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ and $\nu\text{SO}_2\text{OH}$, respectively. In the metal chelates the $\nu\text{C}=\text{N}$ is lowered to 1590-1580 cm^{-1} suggesting involvement of azomethine nitrogen in chelation. Appearance of a band in the range 410-420 cm^{-1} suggest metal-nitrogen bondings in the chelates⁸. Formation of M-O bonds due to deprotonation of $-\text{SO}_2\text{OH}$ and enolic $-\text{OH}$ groups is supported by

TABLE I—MOLECULAR WEIGHT, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC MOMENT AND ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION DATA OF BIVALENT METAL CHELATES OF (α -BENZOYL METHYL BENZYLIDENEIMINO)BENZENE SULPHONIC ACID (H_2BB) AND 2-(α -BENZOYL METHYL BENZYLIDENEIMINO) ETHANE SULPHONIC ACID (H_2BE)

Metal Chelates	Hydrated chelates				Pyridine adducts				Molar extinc- tion Coeff. (ϵ) mole ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹	Transitions (Hydrated and Pyridine adducts)		
	Mol. wt. Found	Mol. wt. Calcd.	ΔM ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	μ_{eff} B.M. at 308°K	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹	Mol. wt. Found	Mol. wt. Calcd.	ΔM ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹			μ_{eff} B.M. at 308°K	ν_{max} cm ⁻¹
[MnLX ₂]	473 (427)	486 (438)	5.1 (5.3)	5.93 (5.91)	25300(25100) 29600(30000)	657 (607)	669 (621)	5.2 (5.0)	5.94 (5.90)	25000(25200) 29500(29800)	(52-67) (70-83)	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ E _g (G) ⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ E _g (D) ⁶ T _{2g} → ⁶ E _g (D)
[FeLX ₂]	476 (425)	487 (439)	5.2 (5.9)	5.44 (5.46)	11400(11600)	655 (610)	670 (622)	5.4 (5.7)	5.47 (5.48)	11300(11400)	(66-74)	⁶ T _{2g} → ⁶ E _g (D)
[CoLX ₂]	474 (430)	490 (442)	4.3 (4.2)	4.87 (4.88)	8700(8500) 21700(21500)	660 (612)	672 (642)	4.1 (4.0)	4.85 (4.84)	8800(8400) 21400(21600)	(82-98) (92-103)	⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{2g} (F) ⁴ T _{1g} (F) → ⁴ T _{1g} (P)
[NiLX ₂]	473 (432)	490 (442)	4.2 (4.4)	2.90 (2.89)	13700(13600) 26100(26000)	661 (611)	672 (624)	4.3 (4.1)	2.97 (2.95)	13900(13600) 26400(26200)	(94-109) (99-113)	⁸ A _{2g} → ⁸ T _{1g} (F) ⁸ A _{2g} → ⁸ T _{1g} (P)
[CuLX ₂]	482 (432)	494 (446)	6.6 (6.7)	1.91 (1.93)	12900(13100)	664 (614)	677 (629)	6.5 (6.4)	1.90 (1.92)	13200(13000)	(118-137)	² E _g → ² T _{2g}
[ZnLX]	450 (401)	461 (413)	3.7 (3.5)	—	—	510 (461)	522 (474)	3.6 (3.4)	—	—	—	—
[CdLX]	495 (445)	507 (459)	3.5 (3.3)	—	—	554 (509)	568 (520)	3.7 (3.2)	—	—	—	—
[PdLX]	490 (441)	501 (453)	6.1 (6.3)	—	22100(22000) 26300(26500) 30400(30200)	548 (504)	562 (514)	6.5 (6.9)	—	22000(22300) 26400(26500) 30400(30500)	— — —	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ B _{1g} ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ E _{1g} ¹ A _{1g} → ¹ A _{2g}
[UO ₂ LX]	653 (605)	665 (617)	7.3 (7.2)	—	—	713 (666)	726 (678)	7.1 (7.0)	—	—	—	—
[VOLX ₂]	468 (420)	480 (432)	6.8 (6.9)	1.67 (1.65)	11600(11400) 19900(19300)	589 (543)	602 (554)	6.7 (6.8)	1.68 (1.70)	11800(11900) 20000(20100)	(112-127) (149-167)	d _{xy} → d _{xz, yz} d _{xy} → d _{x²-y², z²}

Where L = (C₂₁H₁₅NSO₄) or (C₁₇H₁₃NSO₄) and X = H₂O or Py.

The values shown in the parenthesis are those of the corresponding metal chelates of 2-(α -benzoylmethyl benzylideneimino) ethane sulphonic acid.

All the chelates gave satisfactory C, H, N, S, metal and water or pyridine analysis.

When $n = 1$, $M(II) = Zn, Cd, Pd$ or UO_2
 $n = 2$, $M(II) = VO$.
 $n = 3$, $M(II) = Mn, Fe, Co, Ni$ or Cu .

Fig. 1. Bivalent metal chelates of (α -benzoylmethyl-benzylideneimino) benzene sulphonic acid [H_2BB] and 2-(α -benzoylmethyl-benzylideneimino) ethane sulphonic acid [H_2BE],

the appearance of bands in the range 510-530 cm⁻¹. All the chelates gave one broad band in the region 3260-3320 cm⁻¹ due to νOH of water⁹. The loss of water molecules at a relatively high temperature suggest that these are coordinated and not lattice held.

Based on the above evidences Mn(II), Fe(II), Co(II), Ni(II), UO₂²⁺ and VO²⁺-chelates may display an octahedral stereochemistry. Zn(II) and

Cd(II)-chelates possess tetrahedral configuration as they actually do. Pd(II)-chelates show square-planar whereas Cu(II)-chelates may display distorted octahedral geometry in terms of Jahn-Teller effect. Their structures may be represented by Fig. 1.

The similarity in the nature of the metal chelates of H_2BB and H_2BE is due to the presence of azomethine nitrogen atom in β -position to the sulphonic group.

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